

Influence of Leadership Factors on Integration of ICT in Teaching and Learning in TVET Institutions in Uasin Gishu County, Kenya

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Abstract

The study focused on integration of ICT in teaching in Technical and Vocational Education and Training institutions. Mechanical and Automotive Engineering departments were selected because of their high student population in the two sampled institutions hence more representative. The Eldoret National Polytechnic and Rift Valley Technical Training Institute were selected in this study because the two institutions have the highest number of trainees in the County. The objective of this study was to: determine the influence of leadership factors on integration of ICT in teaching and learning. Rodgers' theory of Diffusion of innovation informed the study while questionnaires and interview schedules were used to collect data. The target population consisted of trainers from the Eldoret National Polytechnic and Rift Valley Technical Institute. The sample size for the trainees was 384 which was calculated by fisher's formula and was selected using the simple random sampling whereas 52 trainers were selected using purposive sampling. Data was analyzed by use of Statistical Package for the Social Sciences software. The study findings revealed that ICT integration is not a shared vision between the administration and trainers; administration doesn't provide individual trainers with support for ICT integration; also, they don't provide enough technical support for trainers. The study in general concludes that there is limited use of ICT in teaching. The study recommends that TVET institutions should provide trainers with motivation such as incentives and awards also more technical support so that trainers can make more use of ICT in teaching.

Key Words: ICT, Integration, TVET, Diffusion

Background to the Study

One of the significant changes in the world today is the emergence of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) during the second half of the 20th century, in which the computer and the internet are now being highly used to procure, process, store, communicate and apply information/knowledge. With the emergence of this information age, the world has become a global village with global interconnectedness, with internal and international borders becoming bridges (Adewunmi, 2012). Many societies in the developed as well as in the developing countries are using these devices to build up knowledge as a new weapon for rivalry and growth, for example, fighting against poverty, access to education and health services, transformation and modernization of the economy, the government and the entire society (Hare, 2007). Castells (2001) says that, ICTs act upon all domains of human activity and make it possible for endless connections to be established between different domains, as well as between elements and agents of such activities.

Tertiary education institutions, national governments, and international organizations have put a lot of emphasis on the importance of ICTs in today's society, with their teachings, training, and integration. Even though Oliver (2003) asserted that education in particular has not actually felt the impact of ICTs, the situation has changed from then and today, health education, economic education, engineering education, military education, now depend on the new ICTs for research, communication, and application of research results. Ayoo (2009) remarks that ICTs at the same time continue to impact on all aspects of contemporary education, requiring tertiary education institutions and stakeholders to be linked to each other through an advanced network that is connected to the global village. Trainees and teachers, and researchers now interact online without necessarily meeting face-to-face frequently. Some universities today example Mount Kenya University operate as virtual universities or with virtual libraries. The new technologies have led to the development of off-campus degree programs, new forms of learning in different environments or settings. For instance, today we hear of the use of e-learning, blended learning, and open and distance learning.

ICT Integration in Technical Training

The technical education sector in Africa has suffered from many deficiencies including quality training, contents, infrastructure, environment etc. Marope, et al, (2015). So, at present, the greatest challenges to be faced by African technical training sector is to create a 'competency-

based education training (CBET) in technical education sector' and ensure that the trainees are equipped with the required competence technically, in terms of knowledge and skills. There is a big potential of using ICT in the development of the technical and vocational education training (TVET) in Africa. Several challenges are likely to be encountered when integrating ICT with CBET training. The challenges according to this research includes but not limited to lack of proper policies on the use of ICT in training, inadequate training of lecturers on the use of ICT in training, Negative attitude of lecturers towards the use of ICT in training and lack of continuous updating of these ICT skills amongst the lecturers. African TVET institutions cannot participate in the global competency-based education training revolution if the trainers and learners lack ICT skills on their instructional activities, inappropriate instructional materials to meet the objectives of training and learning, inadequate motivational techniques to increase the interest to learn. Also lack of training of the lecturers on use of ICT in training is a major barrier to improve the quality of the technical and vocational education training.

Updating of these skills may improve the quality of the present TVET training. Africa must prepare itself to compete effectively in the global technical training market

Government should provide enough budgets to ensure the requirement of ICT tools and machineries for each classroom. Government should formulate proper policy to train up the lecturers for their respective field as well as in ICT. Lecturers' motivation is a critical factor in use of ICT adoption. Policies in this area should include measures raising the confidence levels of the lecturers (by giving appropriate in-service and initial teacher training on ICT) and also by rewarding them for the use of ICT (Songa, 2015).

All these indicate that there is an existing knowledge gap as far as the use of ICTs in teaching in African tertiary education in concerned. For TVET and their countries to bridge this gap as AAU (2009) reiterated, their individual situations in terms of views, barriers, and actual use must be identified and studied so that measures can be taken. This study sought to contribute to this knowledge gap.

Statement of the Problem

Computers are spreading rapidly in schools not just in developed countries, but increasingly in developing ones as well. However, although TVET have had computers for over two decades, ways to use them effectively have evolved slowly. Technological revolution in schools has

been beset by theoretical inadequacies that have kept educational technology at the margins of the established educational system. Research findings in Kenya have revealed that there are ICT facilities in the TVET sector such as computers, computer laboratories, internet connections, alongside the traditional methods of telecommunication. Further research has revealed that teachers do not make real use of ICTs at their disposal hence weak integration and usage in classroom activities-teaching and learning.

In addition, most TVET institutions in Kenya are in the rural areas and they face a number of challenges including; high levels of poverty, limited rural electrification and frequent power disruptions, inadequate connectivity and network infrastructure. This creates a digital divide between the rural and the urban colleges as well as the developed and the developing countries. Failure to take full advantage of the opportunities offered by technological advances to education for massive expansion represent a drastic lag in skilled innovative manpower narrowing the possibilities for individual activities in areas of business, research, The study sought to establish the factors that affect the integration of ICT in TVET institutions in Uasin Gishu County.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this study was to investigate the leadership factors that influence integration of ICT in teaching and learning in TVET institutions in Uasin Gishu County.

Conceptual Framework

In this study the independent variables are administrative support and technical support whereas ACT integration is the dependent variable.

Independent Variables

Dependent Variable

Literature Review

Theoretical framework

The study was based on Roger's theory of Diffusion of Innovations. The theory seeks to explain how, why, and at what rate new ideas and technology spread through cultures. Diffusion research centers on the conditions which increase or decrease the likelihood that a new idea, product, or practice is adopted by members of a given culture or a social system. This was extended by Rogers (2003) hence at present is commonly known as Roger's theory of diffusion of innovation

Integration of ICT in TVET in Kenya

The Kenya Vision 2030 is a vehicle for accelerating transformation of our country into a rapidly industrialized middle-income nation by the year 2030. TVET has emerged as one of the most effective human resource development strategies that Kenya need to embrace in order to train and modernize their technical workforce for rapid industrialization and national development. The argument is that in order for technical and vocational education to effectively support industrialization, skills training must be of high quality and competency-based (Wanyeki, 2012). Kenya vision 2030 is a long-term development blueprint for the country and it's anchored on three key pillars namely, economic, social and political.

It is also anchored on the following foundations; macroeconomic stability, continuity in governance reforms, enhanced equity and wealth creation opportunities for the poor infrastructure, energy, STI, land reforms, human resource development, security and public sector reforms (Republic of Kenya, 2007). All this is achievable by producing a globally competitive work in TVET. As noted by Wanyeki (2012), Vision 2030 has made it clear that Kenya must be industrialized by the year 2030. Simply put, it is having highly developed tertiary and quaternary sector of industries. It is also important to note that development in a country is also based on human resource development index. This will be done through specialized training at different levels; community polytechnics, and the technical, industrial, vocational and entrepreneurship (Republic of Kenya, 2007)

The social pillar of education and training sector has the following reforms to improve training in the TVET sector; upgrade institutions to enable them to provide training in some skills consistent with emerging technologies, government to accredit private TVET institutes among others.

The government through the ministry of ICT has come up with a National ICT policy that is missioned to facilitate universal access to ICT infrastructure and services all over the country. According to Anderson and Dexter (2005), leadership is one of the several critical strategies in the successful integration of ICT in education and training. Yee (2000) as cited by Tan (2010) believes that a leader who implements technology plans and also shares a common vision with the teachers stimulate them to use technology in their lessons. Wong and Li (2008) conducted a study on factors that influenced transformational integration of ICT in eight schools in Hong Kong and Singapore. The study revealed that leadership promotion of collaboration and experimentation and teachers' dedication to student-centered learning influenced effective ICT transformation. In a quantitative study conducted by Ng (2008) on aspects of transformational leadership with 80 Singaporean secondary teachers, he found that a transformational leadership with qualities of identifying and articulating a vision, promoting acceptance of group goals, providing individualized support, offering intellectual stimulation, providing an appropriate model, creating high performance expectations, and strengthening school culture could influence the integration of ICT.

Mead and Herd (2015) reports the following in the UNESCO World Report: The promise and potential of ICT in TVET, that practitioners' agencies report the critical success factor of commitment and leadership from institutional heads (EU, 2005; Cinterfor, 2008; COL 2011).

Without a strong leadership which ensures inclusion of strategic objectives in planning processes, creates appropriate organized structure, supports the strengthening of ICT infrastructure and focuses on staff capacity building, ICT initiatives can't succeed. Further, Cinterfor states in a study of ICT integration in TVET in Latin American countries, it was discovered that the new ICT has made it possible for knowledge in Vocational Training Institutes to be disseminated quickly but this has gotten a boost by the active interest shown by directors and heads of programs (CINTERFOR 2008:15)

Technical support

Similarly, Yilmaz, (2011) in assessing the technology integration processes in the Turkish education system reported that in providing schools with hardware and internet connections, it is also crucial to provide the schools with technical support with regard to repair and maintenance for the continued use of ICT in schools. Jones (2004) as cited by Guma, Faruque and Khushi, (2013) reported that the breakdown of a computer causes interruptions and if there is lack of technical assistance, then it is likely that the regular repairs of the computer will not be carried out resulting in teachers not using computers in teaching. The effect is that teachers will be discouraged from using computers because of fear of equipment failure since no one would give them technical support in case there is technical problem.

Becta (2004) agreed that “if there is a lack of technical support available in a school, then it is likely that technical maintenance will not be carried out regularly, resulting in a higher risk of technical breakdowns”. Neyland (2011) as cited by Saina et al. (2018) in assessing the technology integration processes in Turkish education system reported that in providing TVET institutions with ICT hardware and software, it is also crucial to provide them with technical support such as repair and maintenance. Therefore, if there is no technical support for teachers, they become frustrated resulting in their unwillingness to use ICT (Tong & Trinidad, 2005).

Research Methodology

Non-experimental descriptive survey design was used. In this study, the target population consisted of trainees and trainers at The Eldoret National Polytechnic and Rift Valley Technical Institute.. This study used purposive sampling. Data was collected using questionnaires Validity is a measure of how well a test measures what it is supposed to measure (Kombo, 2006; Orodho, 2009; Mugenda, 1999). Validity was established through close consultation and expert judgment of other experienced researchers. A pilot study was conducted at the Eldoret

Technical Training Institute to test reliability and a reliability index of 0.89 was obtained, the scores were checked against a 0.5 level of significance and therefore found to be reliable few corrections were made on the questions that were unclear and these were duly done.

Findings and Discussion

Leadership Factors

The respondents were probed in order for the researcher to establish if the administration supported them and whether trainers had adequate technical support, the following was the response obtained;

Administrative support

Table 1.1 Trainers perspective

The target population of the trainers was 52 and 51 responses were received. The responses of trainers in this study was tabulated in frequency and their percentages as follows:

Factor	SA	A	U	D	SD
Integration of ICT in teaching and learning is a shared vision between the administration and trainers	0 0	1 1.96	0 0	46 90.20	4 7.84
The administration provides individual trainers with support for integration of ICT in teaching and learning	0 0	0 0	0 0	48 94.12	3 5.88
The administration provides regular in-service training for trainers for effective integration of ICT in teaching and learning	0 0	0 0	0 0	51 100	0 0
The administration provides regular motivation and incentives for integration of ICT in teaching and learning.	0 0	0 0	0 0	46 90.20	4 7.84
The administration regularly monitors and evaluates the integration of ICT in teaching and learning.	0 0	0 0	0 0	45 88.24	6 11.76

Discussion

Table 1.1 reveals that the trainers disagreed that Integration of ICT in teaching and learning is a shared vision between the administration and trainers. The administration does not provide

individual trainers with support for integration of ICT in teaching and learning. the administration also does not provide regular in-service training for trainers for effective integration of ICT in teaching and learning. the administration doesn't provide regular motivation and incentives for integration of ICT in teaching and learning and that the administration does not do regular monitoring and evaluation the integration of ICT in teaching and learning. Lack of support from the administration has led to the low usage of technology in teaching.

Technical Support

Table 1.2 Technicians' Perspective

Factor	SA	A	U	D	SD
Too much work and you are overstretched	0	100	0	0	0
The administration provides all the required software and hardware	0	0	0	100	0
The administration provides regular in-service training	0	0	0	100	0
The administration provides regular motivation and incentives	0	0	0	50	50

The technicians revealed that they are overstretched; the administration did not provide all the required software and hardware, regular in-service training and motivation and incentives. This made it difficult for them to support trainers in using ICT for teaching and learning processes. The administrators agreed in unison that the technicians were inadequate, finances to provides all the required software and hardware, provide in service training and motivation was insufficient.

The findings agree with Bingimlas (2009) who established barriers to ICT integration. He states that teachers should be provided with technical support for excellent integration of ICT in learning and teaching opportunities.

Conclusion

The findings reveal that trainers disagreed that Integration of ICT in teaching and learning is a shared vision between the administration and trainers, also that the administration provides individual trainers with support for integration of ICT in teaching and learning. Apart from that, the leadership doesn't provide enough technical support for trainers.

Recommendations

Based on the research findings and the discussion, the study formulated recommendations; TVET institutions should provide trainer with motivation such as incentives and awards for trainers who use ICT in teaching this will in turn motivate trainers hence more use of ICTs also, they should provide more technicians in order to provide technical support more effectively so as trainers can make more use of ICT in teaching.

Suggestions for Further Research

Further research should be carried out to find out other factors that affect ICT integration, assess the impact of ICT integration for instruction on TVET education and to ascertain the positive influence of the use of ICTs in the teaching and learning process.

References

- Adewunmi, Y.H. (2012). Developing a sustainable approach to corporate FM in Nigeria. *Facilities*.
- Bauer, J., & Kenton, J. (2005). Toward technology integration in the schools: Why it isn't happening. *Journal of technology and teacher education*, 13(4), 519-546.
- Buabeng-Andoh, C. (2012). Factors influencing teacher's adoption and integration of information and communication technology into teaching: A review of the literature. *International Journal of Education and Development using ICT*, 8(1).
- Castells, G. (2008). The impact of new ICT on democracy: positive and negative scenarios. *Socialiniai mokslai*, (1), 81-92.
- GOK, (2007). *A globally Competitive and Prosperous Kenya. Vision 2030*
- Hare, P. M. (2007). Internal conversion to the electronic ground state occurs via two distinct pathways for pyrimidine bases in aqueous solution. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 104(2), 435-440.
- Kay, R. (2006). Addressing gender differences in computer ability, attitudes and use: The laptop effect. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 34(2), 187-211.
- Kombo, D. K., & Delno, L. A. (2006). *An Introduction to Thesis Writing*.
- Kothari, C. R. (1985). *Research Methodology: Methods and techniques*, 5th, 6th editions. *New Delhi, India*.

- Kotsik, B., Tokareva, N., Boutin, F., & Chinien, C. (2009). ICT application in TVET. In *International handbook of education for the changing world of work* (pp. 1879-1894). Springer, Dordrecht.
- Kotsik, B., Tokareva, N., Boutin, F., & Chinien, C. (2009). ICT application in TVET. In *International handbook of education for the changing world of work* (pp. 1879-1894). Springer, Dordrecht.
- Kushnir, N., Manzhula, A., & Valko, N. (2014, June). Future and experienced teachers should collaborate on ICT integration. In *International Conference on Information and Communication Technologies in Education, Research, and Industrial Applications* (pp. 217-237). Springer, Cham.
- Lau, B. T., & Sim, C. H. (2008). Exploring the extent of ICT adoption among secondary school teachers in Malaysia. *International Journal of Computing and ICT research*, 2(2), 19-36.
- Levin, T., & Wadmany, R. (2008). Teachers' views on factors affecting effective integration of information technology in the classroom: Developmental scenery. *Journal of Technology and Teacher Education*, 16(2), 233-263.
- Markauskaite, L. (2006). Gender issues in preservice teachers' training: ICT literacy and online learning. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 22(1).
- Marope, Priscilla Toka Mmantsetsa, Borhène Chakroun, and K. P. Holmes. *Unleashing the potential: Transforming technical and vocational education and training*. UNESCO Publishing, 2015.
- Mugenda, O. M. and Mugenda, A. G. (2003). *Research Methods. Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*. Nairobi: acts press.
- Oliver, R. (2003). Exploring benchmarks and standards for assuring quality online teaching and learning in higher education.
- Orodho, J.A. (2009). *Essentials of Education and Social Science Research Techniques of Writing Research Proposal and Reports in*
- Robinson, L. (2009). *A summary of diffusion of innovations*.
- Rogers, E.M. (2003). *Diffusion of innovations* (5th ed.). New York: Free Press.
- Sandholtz, J. H., & Reilly, B. (2004). Teachers, not technicians: Rethinking technical expectations for teachers. *Teachers College Record*, 106(3), 487-512.
- Songa, F. T. O. (2015). Information technology as a strategy in enhancing competency based

